

Status of Fish Culture in Joypurhat District, Northern Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out for a period of seven months (January 2006 to July 2006) from 50 farm owners and 50 local people near the farms of different Upazilla (Joypurhat sadar, Panchbibi, Akkelpur, Khetlal and Kalai) in Joypurhat district. The study indicated that most of the farms (46%) were established within last ten years. Fifteen different fish species were cultured. Three types of farm were observed, such as own (48%), leased (38%) and both (14%). Fish farming (58%) was the major income source for farm owners. Most of the (72%) farms depend on underground water. Various types of chemicals and toxic substances like rotenone (16% farm), phostoxin (10% farm), bleaching powder (6% farm), disel/kerosin (22% farm) and sumithion (4% farm) were used. Among all the farms 32%, 56% and 34% were affected by tail and fin rot, oxygen deficiency and disease, respectively. Lime (76% farm), salt (34%) and sumithion (18%) were widely used as antibiotics for disinfection, prevention and control of fish disease. Total fish productions have gradually been increased in all the farms. The benefits of fish farm owners were increased in income (92% farm owners), social status (74% farm owners), employment opportunity (58% farm owners), ingestion of fish (42% farm owners) and poverty alleviation (70% farm owners).

Key words: fish farm, fish production, Joypurhat district.

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh has extensive wetlands that form an important fisheries resource, which is very much potential for production of fish and fishery items. The total water resources of the country are estimated as 46, 99,345 ha of inland water [5] that comprises of rivers, tributaries, estuaries, beels, haors, baors, ponds, lakes, tanks etc. About 2.46% of the total export earning is contributed by fisheries sector [6] Fish and fisheries play a vital role in the socio-economic development, fulfilling the demand of animal protein, opportunity for employment, poverty alleviation of large number of population and earning foreign currency. Bangladesh is ranked 3rd in the aquatic bio-diversity in Asia behind China and India, with approximately 300 species of fresh and brackish water species [8]. Fish production from inland open water has been decreasing due to various reasons such as changing aquatic ecosystem, soil erosion, siltation in the river, construction of dam to control flood and irrigation, indiscriminate use of agro-chemicals, destructive fishing practices, over fishing etc. Cultural fish production has come from a variety of farms ranging

from small-scale owner-operated fish ponds to large scale co-operative and corporate farms, supported by auxiliary industries such as feed and equipment manufacture. Fishes are cultured traditional extensive techniques in Bangladesh but now fish farmers are adopting scientific technologies instead of ancient culture methods. The present study was planned to know the status of fish culture in ponds of the study area. The proper production can be estimated with focusing the importance of pond in freshwater inland fish culture. Better fish production would be able to supply fish protein to the poor selection of the population and thus will increase the annual intake of protein of the population of our country. Therefore, the study was carried out to find out the status of fish culture in Joypurhat district, Northern Bangladesh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out for a period of seven months (January 2006 to July 2006) of different Upazilla (Joypurhat sadar, Panchbibi, Akkelpur, Khetlal and Kalai) of Joypurhat district. The data for this study were collected by questionnaire interviews through simple random sampling method. A total of 50 farm owner (Joypurhat sadar: 14, Panchbibi: 11, Akkelpur: 8, Khetlal: 9 and Kalai: 8) were selected randomly for interview. All the data were analyzed by computer software MS excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farm establishment year and type

The surveyed farms were established from 1974 to 2006 (Table. 2). It is found that 46% farms were established from 1996 to 2005, 24% were established from 1986 to 1990 and 30% were established from 1974 to 1985. Among all the surveyed farms 28% were homestead and 72% were commercial.

Size and category of land ownership of farms

The surveyed fish farms were three categories such as small farm (up to 2.0 ha), medium farm (2.1 to 8.0 ha) and large farm (8.1 to above). Surveyed fish farms were classified into three categories according to the ownership pattern of land use such as own (48%), leased (38%) and both (14%). It has been observed

that 56% farms were established on agriculture land. Pillay (1992) reported that productive agricultural land is an idea site for fish farms, but such land is not easily available for fish culture [10]. For this reason there is a possibility to arise conflict between the farm owners and land owners. Rahman (1986) also stated that land use and land leased conflict were major constrains to the development of fish culture in Bangladesh [11].

Fish culture as an income source of farm owners

It was observed that fish farming was the primary income source for 58% farm owner and secondary income source for 42% farm owners.

Sources and depth of water

It was observed that 72% farms depend on underground water and rest 28% farm depends on surface water for fish culture in the study area. It was also observed that minimum water depth of 66% farms was 1.25-2.0 m and 34% farms were 2.1- 2.5 m respectively.

Species cultured in farms

A large number of species were cultured in the study area, both indigenous and exotic car-ps. The highest percentage (98%) of the fishes was *Labeo rohita* and *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* and lowest (6%) was *Clarias batrachus*. The cultured species and percentage distributions of farms are presented in Table 1.

Table-1: Cultured species and percentage distributions of farms of the studied area

Group	Local Name	Scientific Name	Percentage (%)
Exotic Carp	Catla	<i>Catla catla</i>	96
	Rui	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	98
	Mrigel	<i>Cirrhinus mrigala</i>	90
	Kalbaush	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	56
	Silver carp	<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	98
	Mirror carp	<i>Cyprinus carpio var specularis</i>	72
	Grass carp	<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	64
	Sarputi	<i>Puntius gonionotus</i>	66
	Thai pangus	<i>Pungasius sutchi</i>	60
	Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis mossambica</i>	42
	Common carp	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	38
	Bighead carp	<i>Aristichthys nobilis</i>	12
Minor carp	Bata	<i>Labeo bata</i>	20
Catfish	Shing	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>	8
	Magur	<i>Clarias batrachus</i>	6

Major inputs

Various types of chemicals and toxic substances like rotenone (16% farm), phostoxin (10% farm), bleaching powder (6% farm),

disel/kerosin (22 % farm) and sumituion (4% farm) were used in the studied farms for the controlling of aquatic weeds, pests, predators and undesirable species during pond preparation (Table. 3). Uses of organic are an important means of nutrient supplement in order to produce natural food in the pond. It was found that

almost all the farms, 86% used urea, 82% used TSP, 92% used cow dung, 66% used MP, 84% used poultry excreta, 8% used compost and only 4% used gypsum of the studied farm (Table. 3). Supply of supplementary feeds and nutrients is a rising trend to increase farm fish production. In the studied fish farm the most uses of supplementary feeds were mustard oil cake (96% farms), rice bran (90%) and wheat bran (64%) (Table. 3). Mazid and Banu

stated that indiscriminate and unplanned use of feed and fertilizer increase stress of fish and accelerates susceptibility to pathogen [9]. So, there is a possibility to appear such types of adverse impacts of aquaculture in the surveyed farms. [1] stated that environmental impacts depend on the amount of food given to the fishes, the mode of feeding, and the fish density and per unit production.

Table.2: Year- wise total and average fish production in the studied fish farm

Year	Total area under culture (ha)	Total production (MT)	Yield (kg/ha/yr)
2000-01	35.65	76	2130
2001-02	37.27	84	2254
2002-03	45.87	124	2703
2003-04	51.45	147	2857
2004-05	57.78	177	3063
2005-06	62.97	217	3446

Table.3: Uses of fertilizers, feeds, nutrients and chemicals of studied farm

Uses of fertilizers		Uses of feeds and nutrients		Uses of chemicals	
Name	% of farms	Name	% of farms	Name	% of farms
Urea	86	Rice bran	90	Rotenone	16
TSP	82	Rice Polish	56	Phostoxin	10
MP	66	Wheat bran	64	Bleaching powder	06
Cowdung	92	Wheat flour	42	Disel/kerosi n	22
Poultry excreta	84	Mustard oil cake	96		
Compost	08	Banana leaf	20		
Gypsum	04	Fish meal	36	Sumithion	04

Water exchange and discharging

It is essential to exchange the wastewater from the farm to keep the quality of farm water and to get the optimum production. In the studied fish farm 52% farm owners were exchanged farm water and 48% didn't exchange. In the studied area 33.77% were discharged water into surrounding area, 15.38% discharged into the canal and 11.54% discharged into the river. Various changes were observed due to the discharge of farm effluents in the receiving water area. It was observed that 22% farms were involved to increase the productivity of receiving area, 42% involved to increase turbidity, 6% involved to increase mud, 8% involved to deteriorate fishery and 10% involved to bad smell or odour.

Disease outbreak and prevention

Result shows that 32%, 56% and 34% farms were affected by tail and fin rot, oxygen deficiency disease and argulosis, respectively. Several chemicals and antibiotics like lime (76% farm), salt (34%) and sumithion (18%) are widely used for disinfection, prevention and control of fish disease. Highly infected or dead fishes were thrown into the open environment (65% farm), put under the soil (22.50% farm), sold (7.5% farm) and given to the local people (5% farm). Pillay (1992) stated that

there is a possibility of generating drug-resistant strains of pathogens by the use of antibiotics for treating diseases into the environment. As the resistance to antibiotic can be transmitted from one bacterium to another, there is a risk of transference of antibiotic resistance to normal bacteria in the human gut if antibiotic resistant bacteria are ingested in numbers. Boyd and Masscout reported about the risks associated with the use of chemicals in pond aquaculture[3].

Production of fish

Fish production was continuously increasing (Table 2) in the surveyed area. It is clear that total productions have gradually increased and per unit fish production (kg/ha) also increased. In 2005-2006 the production was 3446 kg/ha/yr [2]. stated that per unit fish production was 4816 kg/ha/yr which is higher than the present study. The lower production in study area may be due to acidic soil, turbid water and inadequate water during dry seasons etc. (DoF, 2003). However, increased fish production was being achieved by the expansion of farm numbers, area of land and water under culture and the use of more intensive and modern farming technology that involve higher usage of inputs such as water, feeds, fertilizers and chemicals. The number of farms is increasing in each year which is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Year wise increasing farms of the surveyed area Benefits of Farm owners and local people

Benefits of Farm owners and local people

The benefits fish farm owners after establishing the farm were increased income (92% farm owners), increased social status (74% farm owners), employment opportunity (58% farm owners), increased ingestion of fish (42% farm owners) and poverty alleviation (70% farm owners). Local people were benefited from fish farm in many ways. It was found that the benefits were employment opportunity (38%), increase technical knowledge (20%) and motivation towards fish culture (22%), poverty alleviation (12%), increased ingestion of fish and obtain more money through leasing their land (8%). Dhawan et al, stated that aquaculture farming as one of the promising industry improved quality of life of the rural population through direct impact on their socio-economic status [4].

Problems

Several problems of fish farming were identified in the study area. It was found that technical problems were non-availability of land (24%), lack of scientific and technical knowledge (42%), acidic soil (24%) and fewer co-operations of concerned agencies (18%), turbidity (44%) and attack of fish diseases (24%) and deterioration of quality seed (40%). Habib et al. recorded the similar problems of pond fish culture in an area of Bangladesh [7]. The economic problems were high price of various inputs (36%), low product price (20%), lack of credit facilities (32%), lack of marketing facilities (18%), loss of fish during flood (14%) and lack of capital (64%). The social problems were theft of fish and poisoning in the pond water, which were problems of 66% and 24% farm owners, respectively. Saha (2003) stated that theft, poisoning, lack of capital and technical knowledge were the major problems of aquaculture in the Dinajpur district [12].

CONCLUSION

It is clear that long term and sustainable development can be achieved only through sound environmental management and the status of fish culture of Joypurhat was not satisfactory. But this experience will help the aquaculturists to improve the culture status and increase fish production with the find out of the solutions of the identified problems.

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